

Analysis plan

German adaptation: Emulation of efficacy of liraglutide versus placebo on metabolic outcomes

Reddie WP4

Responsible partner: UULM

Work package: 4 (Leader Christian Torp-Pedersen)

Main authors: Stefanie Schmid, Stefanie Lanzinger

Version: 1

Purpose

To emulate efficacy trials regarding GLP1-RA in national registers, inspired by LEAD-2 and LEAD-3.

Background

Beyond cardiovascular outcomes, several phase III studies investigated the safety and efficacy of GLP1-RAs. In the following, two of those studies are presented.

LEAD-2 investigated liraglutide as an add-on to metformin treatment, contrasting with metformin and glimepiride (sulfonylurea class) or placebo, in subjects previously treated with oral antidiabetes therapy. LEAD-2 investigated outcomes over 26 weeks. The primary outcome of the LEAD trials was HbA1c. Inclusion criteria were: aged 18-80 years, diagnosed type 2 diabetes, HbA1c of 7-11% (previous OAD monotherapy for at least 3 months) or HbA1c 7-10% (previous OAD combination therapy for at least 3 months), and BMI ≤ 40 kg/m².

LEAD-3 investigated monotherapy of liraglutide versus monotherapy of glimepiride over a time span of two years, one year double-blind randomized, one-year open-label treatment. Outcomes were HbA1c, fasting plasma glucose, and body weight, beyond hypoglycemia and adverse effects.

Inclusion criteria: type 2 diabetes, 18–80 years, body mass index ≤ 45 kg/m², screening HbA1c 7–11% (53–97 mmol/mol) on diet/exercise or 7–10% (53–86 mmol/mol) on oral antidiabetic drug monotherapy.

Primary Objectives

1. To compare changes in HbA1c and BMI after 12 and 24 months between continuous treatment combinations (LEAD-2):
 - metformin + GLP1-RA
 - metformin + sulfonylureas
 - metformin + DPP-4i
2. To compare changes in HbA1c and BMI after 12 and 24 months between continuous monotherapies (LEAD-3)

In case sample size allows, the follow-up time periods 6 and 18 months will be additionally investigated for primary objectives 1 and 2.

Causal parameter of interest

The main outcome is achieving an HbA1c <7.5% after 12 and 24 months and will be compared between different treatment groups. Achieving a BMI reduction of at least 5% will be studied as a secondary outcome.

LEAD-2 inspired analysis

1. What the average difference between the achieved HbA1c would have been after 12 and 24 months, respectively if all patients had been treated continuously with metformin + GLP1-RA versus if all had been treated with metformin + sulfonylureas
2. What the average difference between the achieved HbA1c would have been after 12 and 24 months, respectively if all patients had been treated continuously with metformin + GLP1-RA versus if all had been treated with metformin + DPP-4i
3. What the average difference between the achieved BMI would have been after 12 and 24 months, respectively if all patients had been treated continuously with metformin + GLP1-RA versus if all had been treated with metformin + sulfonylureas
4. What the average difference between the achieved BMI would have been after 12 and 24 month, respectively s if all patients had been treated continuously with metformin + GLP1-RA versus if all had been treated with metformin + DPP-4i

LEAD-3

1. What the average difference between the achieved HbA1c would have been after 12 and 24 months, respectively if all patients had been treated continuously with GLP1-RA as first-line monotherapy versus if all had been treated with the comparator
2. What the average difference between the achieved BMI would have been after 12 and 24 months, respectively if all patients had been treated continuously with GLP1-RA as first-line monotherapy versus if all had been treated with the comparator

Data sources

The registry data as specified:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1_mZ1j1vX39wyL65BAQSRIEZTC7E09NmZPryq3qS9mAw/edit#heading=h.smy54dsbq27t

Study population inspired by LEAD-2

Period of interest is Jan 2010 to Dec 2023.

Index date (baseline) is the start of add-on treatment or monotherapy and follow them for 12 (+/- 3 months), and 24 months (+/- 3 months).

Inclusion criteria (LEAD-2)

We include all individuals with type 2 diabetes documented in the diabetes prospective follow-up (DPV) registry who initiated as first secondary therapy to metformin either GLP1-RA, sulfonylurea, or DDP-4i and who have had their HbA1c measured a maximum one year prior to baseline (index date) between 7.5 and 11%.

Analyses of BMI require BMI available at baseline or a maximum of one year before baseline (index date).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

LEAD-2 Trial	Emulation with DPV
Adult people with type 2 diabetes between 18 and 80 years of age	Adult people with type 2 diabetes between 18 and 80 years of age with metformin monotherapy prior to index date
HbA1c 7-11% in case of prestudy OAD monotherapy for at least 3 months HbA1c 7-10% in case of prestudy combination therapy for at least 3 months	HbA1c 7.5-11% in the latest measurement max 12 months prior to index date (including index date)
BMI ≤ 40 kg/m ² at screening	BMI ≤ 40 kg/m ² in the latest measurement max 12 months prior to index date (including index date)
Subjects were excluded if they had used insulin during the previous 3 months (except short-term treatment)	People using <i>basal</i> insulin during the previous 3 months as add on to metformin prior to and at index date were not excluded, however any other use of insulin during 3 months prior to index date is a exclusion criteria,

Covariates

The following baseline variables, defined looking back from the index date, are used to control for confounding. Baseline values of the conditions and medical history are obtained based on any occurrence in the 10-year history at the index date.

- Age at index date
- Sex
- German Index of Socioeconomic deprivation (GISD)
- Degree of urbanization (3 levels: rural, suburbs, urban)
- HbA1c: closest prior to the index date, maximum one year prior
- BMI: closest prior to the index date, maximum one year prior
- History of heart failure (Y/N)
- Hypertension (Y/N)

- Ischemic heart disease (Y/N)
- Stroke (Y/N)
- Peripheral artery disease (Y/N)
- Chronic renal disease (Y/N)
- Atrial fibrillation (Y/N)
- Any cancer (Y/N)
- Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Y/N)
- Aldosterone receptor antagonists (Y/N)
- Beta-blocker (Y/N)
- Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor/angiotensin receptor-2 blocker (Y/N)
- Loop diuretics (Y/N)
- Calcium channel blockers (Y/N)
- Thiazide (Y/N)
- Acetylsalicylic acid (Y/N)
- Statins (Y/N)

Outcomes

Within an observational context, patients are not assumed to adhere to the same strict follow-up protocols as in clinical trials. Consequently, we will need to specify definitions of intervals during which the outcomes of HbA1c and BMI can be assessed, assuming to approximate the times observed in trials, outlined as follows:

Figure 1. Outline of study period.

Analyses

The validity of interpretations of analyses derived within the framework of causal inference methods requires the assessment of certain assumptions, commonly denoted as exchangeability, consistency, and positivity. Among these assumptions, the positivity assumption includes an evaluation of both theoretical and practical dimensions. In this context, the descriptive section will address the evaluation of the practical positivity assumption, ie. the coverage in the data. Based on these descriptive analyses of adherence and feasibility of conducting analyses of the specified target parameters will be determined.

Descriptives

The following descriptive inquiries are to be answered:

- Quantification of individuals initiating monotherapy of metformin, sulfonylureas, DPP-4i and GLP1-RA , categorized by calendar year
- Quantification of individuals initiating treatment with metformin + sulfonylureas, metformin + DPP-4i and metformin+GLP1-RA, respectively, categorized by calendar year
- Evaluation of treatment adherence, ie. percentage of individuals maintaining monotherapy or combination therapy with sulfonylureas, DPP-4i, GLP1-RA for durations of 12 and 24 months.
- Assessment of the percentage of individuals initiating the specified treatment regimes who have measurements of Hba1c and BMI at baseline and follow-up (12 and 24 months).

Trial emulation

We will employ a discrete time scale with time periods of 12 months (if sample size allows also 6 months). For the nuisance parameters (outcome models, propensity score models, censoring models) of the target trial emulation, we regress the outcome/treatment/censoring variables as defined in the time intervals on the history up to and including each selected time interval. All nuisance models are fitted using the SuperLearner. The catalog of regression formulas added to the SuperLearner are chosen following outcome-blinded simulations to ensure that the SuperLearner performs as intended. Reported are the LTMLE estimates of average treatment effects with 95% confidence intervals.

Note: This analysis plan will be further elaborated while analysing the data and is based on the overall plan on the emulation of efficacy of liraglutide versus placebo on metabolic outcomes:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Oh2wsDqB56349ymaUB3ZQdkwQ9my992mr5qFi3F8hLU/edit#heading=h.9lrhq03u4zyl>

For reference:

LEAD-2: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18931095/>

LEAD-3: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3084519/>

ATC codes to define glucose-lowering drug classes

Drug class	ATC-codes
Insulin	A10A
Biguanidk	A10BA01, A10BA03, A10BD01
Metformin	A10BA02, A10BD02-3, A10BD05, A10BD07-8, A10B10-11, A10BD20, A10BD22-23, A10BD25-27
Sulfonylurea	A10BB, A10BDO1, A10BD04, A10BDO
Alfa glucosidase inhib	A10BF, A10BD17
Thiazolidinidion	A10BG, A10BD03-06, A10BD09, A10BD12, A10BD26
DPP4	A10BH, A10BD07, A10BD08, A10BD10, A10BD11, A10BD13
SGLT2	A10BK, A10BD15, A10BD16, A10BD20, A10BD23, A10BD27
GLP1-RA	A10BJ, A10AE54, A10AE56